

SIMULATION OF EMBEDDED AND IoT BASED SMART AUTOMATION SYSTEM FOR ELDERLY AND DISABLED PEOPLE

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Abstract— Simulating a smart automated embedded system for monitoring the elderly and disabled is discussed in this article. Physically challenged people have trouble turning on and off lights, fans, and other household appliances, and thus require assistance. A person detector detects authorized individuals and opens or closes the door. The use of an Active RF device allows for automatic door opening and closing by sensing the presence of a person near the entrance. This programme is capable of detecting a person's possible fall. Using sophisticated sensors and a user-friendly interface, relatives, doctors, and other persons who look after the elderly can be alerted.

Keywords—Embedded system, Microcontroller, Global Positioning System, Accelerometer Sensor, Temperature Sensor, Motor drive, Node MCU, DC Motor.

I. INTRODUCTION

The elderly constitutes a significant and growing portion of the global population. Statistics reveal that the percentage of persons aged 65 and over is steadily increasing due to a variety of factors, including decreased birth rates and women's fertility. The proportion of the population aged 65 and up in the United States climbed from 12.4 percent in 2000 to 13.3 percent in 2011, and it is likely to continue to rise to 21% of the population by 2040. Furthermore, today's social lifestyle, modern medicine, and easy access to medical treatment have all contributed to an increase in life expectancy. According to a United Nations report, life expectancy was 65 years in 1950, 78 years in 2010, and is expected to climb to 83 years in 2045. On the other side, in 2011, it was claimed that 35% of adults aged 65 and up had a disability. Some of them require assistance in order to achieve critical personal requirements. Frail older persons prefer to live independently and manage their own affairs in their own homes, which promotes sense of competence and reduces depression risk. In reality, living at home with monitoring devices and intelligent equipment is less expensive and more helpful than visiting medical centres and being watched by nurses from an economic standpoint. Smart home systems with remote monitor controls and health care

capabilities, on the other hand, will lower the cost of personal aid support at home.

The goal of this project is to develop a wireless remote control that allows senior individuals with physical limitations, such as handicapped and disabled individuals, to control their desired equipment without having to travel to a control point. In the not-too-distant future, home automation systems will be very common. By connecting items to the internet, IoT-based home automation will assist the user in using a home appliance. The internet is used to automate modern dwellings. Wireless devices such as computers, tablets, and smartphones are used to operate home appliances. All of these appliances and systems are equipped with sensors that allow them to connect to a network. This is where the Internet of Things comes into play, making it such an important aspect of home automation. Electronic devices, ranging from televisions to surveillance cameras, are now interconnected in almost every home. These devices become IoT when they are connected to various software and an internet connection. IoT-enabled home automation has proven to be incredibly beneficial for physically challenged people in a variety of situations. The embedded IOT technology is combined here to provide an excellent solution for the elderly and crippled.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

Many different technologies have been proposed in the literature, all of which are based on how the control signal is distributed from the end-user remote control to the target appliances via master control panel boards. The first is the Power-line Carrier system, which sends control coded signals through the existing electrical power wire in the home. The command signals are employed in the range of 24 kHz to 500 kHz, whereas the power line transmits AC signals of 50 Hz or 60 Hz. Propagation issues and electronic interference, where noisy signals might be interpolated, are the key limitations. The second technology focuses on household appliances that are connected to a landline phone system (analog telephone service). The technique is straightforward: after establishing and maintaining a dial-up connection for a set period of time, further digits are phoned

up for various functions. Each number combination corresponds to a certain appliance or piece of equipment. This method does not necessitate the use of the internet. Its disadvantage is that it lacks the capacity to inspect the status of equipment. However, digital phone service, also known as VoIP (voice over IP), transmits digital signals through a broadband connection such as DSL or cable modem. This technology allows for voice control, as well as the sending of e-mails and instant messages (instant messages). In order to execute the commands, the incoming message is evaluated, handled, and mnemonic keywords are developed. Infrared light, which is invisible to the naked eye, is mostly employed in home remote controls to send out unidirectional commands from afar. The remote-control handset's infrared pulses should be transmitted to the device in a short and direct line-of-sight. This method is only useful when the transmitter and receiver are close together or separated by a small distance. Bluetooth technology, on the other hand, allows data to be exchanged across short distances while broadcasting a wireless signal that does not require the controller and the device to be facing each other. Bluetooth's range is determined on the type of radio utilised in its implementation. In fact, the most widely used commercial radio is a class 2 radio with a power of 2.5 mw and a range of 10 m. Bluetooth's key advantage over other wireless modalities is that it is supported by PCs, mobile phones, Android devices, and Apple products. Furthermore, the inclusion of a Bluetooth module on the control main board enables for soft access and appliance control. SMS (Short Message Service) control necessitates the use of mobile communication networks in general. The suggested appliances are controlled by a primary control board that can recognize the phone number from which the SMS is received and so classify the mobile phones that have priority access to the automated system. The GSM (Global System for Mobile Communication) model is a hardware circuit that receives text messages via a SIM (Subscriber Identify Model) card. Typically, the message is deciphered and sent to a processing unit based on a microcontroller, which then triggers the relays to toggle the present states of the switches on the appliances.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This paper mixes embedded and IoT technologies, and it explains how to operate devices remotely more easily, as well as what are the key characteristics to consider while managing or controlling them in general. As a controlling unit, a node MCU microcontroller is employed. There are two sections to this project. Switches are used to regulate home appliances such as lights and fans in the first segment. The second segment uses IOT technology to create a safety gadget for the elderly and crippled. We employ a temperature and heart rate sensor to monitor the health of the person in question, and an accelerometer sensor to detect falls. The system can send data to the cloud, and then a web server can access the data from the server, which can then be controlled and monitored using the mobile application, which can also be used as a web application to operate devices remotely over the internet. When a human press the switches, they activate

and send information to the microcontroller, allowing the load, such as a fan or a light, to be controlled remotely via relay board. The relay board functions as a switching logic for ON/OFF operations, and these activities can only take place through this relay board. The sensor data is sent to the cloud in a timely manner via the internet. The panic switch concept is also expanded with the panic switch for emergency scenarios, where the alarm message and the person's position are sent to their relatives as an alert message. In this case, GPS tracking is also implemented utilising IoT technology, with live monitoring capabilities provided by a cloud app.

IV. BLOCK DIAGRAM OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

Fig. 1. Block Diagram – Part 1: Home Appliance Control

Fig. 2. Block Diagram – Part 2: IoT System for Elderly People

V. BLOCK DIAGRAM DESCRIPTION

a. NODE MCU

The NodeMCU (Node Micro Controller Unit) is an open source software and hardware development environment based on the ESP8266, a low-cost System-on-a-Chip (SoC). The Espressif Systems ESP8266 features all of the essential components of a modern computer, including a CPU, RAM, networking (wifi), and even a current operating system and SDK. The ESP8266, on the other hand, is difficult to access and use as a chip. For the most basic functions, such as turning it on or sending a keystroke to the chip's "computer,"

you must solder wires with the necessary analogue voltage to its PINs. You must also programme it in low-level machine instructions that the chip hardware can understand. While this level of integration isn't an issue when the ESP8266 is used as an embedded controller chip in mass-produced devices, it's a significant burden for hobbyists, hackers, or students who wish to utilise it in their own IoT projects. The NodeMCU project, which takes a page from the successful playbooks of Arduino and Raspberry Pi, intends to make ESP8266 development easier. There are two key components on it.

b. GLOBAL POSITIONING SYSTEM (GPS)

The GPS (Global Positioning System) is a satellite-based navigation system with at least 24 satellites. With no subscription fees or setup charges, GPS works in any weather condition, anywhere in the world, 24 hours a day. The satellites were launched into orbit by the US Department of Defense (USDOD) for military purposes, but they were later made accessible for civilian usage in the 1980s. In a precise orbit, GPS satellites circle the Earth twice a day. Each satellite transmits a unique signal and orbital parameters, which GPS systems can decode and calculate the satellite's precise location. This information, together with trilateration, is used by GPS receivers to calculate a user's actual location. The GPS receiver calculates the distance between each satellite by the time it takes to receive a broadcast signal. The receiver can calculate a user's position and show it electronically using distance measurements from a couple additional satellites, allowing you to measure your running route, map a golf course, find your way home, or embark on an adventure anyplace. A GPS receiver must be locked on to the signal of at least three satellites to determine your 2-D position (latitude and longitude) and track movement. The receiver can calculate your 3-D position if there are four or more satellites in view (latitude, longitude and altitude). A GPS receiver will often track eight or more satellites, depending on the time of day and where you are on the earth. Some devices can perform all of this from the palm of your hand. Once your location has been established, your GPS unit can calculate other data such as speed, bearing, track, trip distance, distance to destination, dawn, sunset, and other factors.

c. ACCELEROMETER SENSOR

The ADXL335 is an accelerometer sensor that operates on the Piezoelectric effect. Because of gravitational pull, the ball is intended to move in the direction we tilt the sensor. Piezoelectric components make up the walls. As a result, every time the ball makes contact with the wall, an electric current is generated, which may be interpreted as values in any 3D area. The ADX1335 is a triple axis accelerometer, which means it will produce three values. The purpose of analogue interfacing is to communicate with other devices such as Arduino. This small device can be used in motion detection projects, gesture control robots, smart phones, and smart watches, among other things.

d. DC MOTOR

The direct current motor is symbolised by the circle in the middle, on which the brushes are fixed, and where the external terminals are connected, from which supply voltage is provided. We have a shaft coming out of the motor and connected to the armature on the mechanical terminal, and the armature-shaft is attached to the mechanical load. We represent the armature resistance R_a in series on the supply terminals. Allow the input voltage E to be placed across the brushes at this point. In the presence of a magnetic field, an electric current flowing through the rotor armature via brushes produces a torque T_g . The dc motor armature rotates due to the torque T_g . The armature conductors carry currents, and the armature rotates inside the stator magnetic field, producing an emf E_b in a manner similar to that of a generator.

e. PUSH BUTTON

A basic switch mechanism for controlling some part of a machine or process is a push-button (sometimes written pushbutton) or simply button. Buttons are commonly composed of hard materials such as plastic or metal. Typically, the surface is flat or contoured to accommodate the human finger or hand, allowing it to be easily depressed or pushed. Although many un-biased buttons still require a spring to return to their un-pushed state, most buttons are biased switches. Pressing, depressing, mashing, slapping, pounding, and punching are all terms for "pushing" a button. Calculators, push-button telephones, kitchen appliances, and a variety of other mechanical and electronic gadgets, both household and commercial, have all used the "push-button." Push buttons can be mechanically linked together in industrial and commercial applications so that pressing one button releases the other. A stop button can "force" a start in this fashion. This type of linkage is utilised in simple manual tasks where the equipment or process is not controlled by electrical circuits.

f. EMBEDDED SYSTEMS

Electronic gadget that is intelligent, programmable, and computing that is designed to accomplish certain tasks within a set time limit. An embedded system is a system that combines hardware and software, as well as mechanical and other components, to accomplish a specified goal. A microprocessor or a microcontroller is commonly used in electronics. General-purpose mainframe computers are used in some large or elderly systems. This type of linkage is utilised in simple manual tasks where the equipment or process is not controlled by electrical circuits.

Fig. 3. Embedded system design

g. **INTERNET OF THINGS**

A dynamic overall association of establishment with own structuring constraints subject to fixed and interoperable symmetricalness models in which analogue and virtual items have personalities, physical characteristics, and virtual personalities, employ sharp interfaces, and are reliably planned into the information sort out. The Internet of Things is characterised by a dynamic overall organise structure with self-structure limits depletion on standard standards, interoperable correspondence traditions in which physical and virtual "Equivalent words/Hyponyms (Ordered by Estimated Frequency) of item" have personalities, physical and virtual personalities, employ clever interfaces, and are reliably planned into the informatic orchestrate. IoT has progressed from being a Synonyms/Hyponyms (Ordered by Estimated Frequency) of cutting-edge vision - with the occasional particular dimension of progression - to a rising basic supply world in the last twelve months. Telecom officials believe the internet is transitioning into an internal business priority, citing a significant increase in the number of linked enquiries in the industry. Manufacturers of wearable comfort devices, for example, are anticipating a whole new market segment devoted to the IoT. These geographic campaign results are currently making progress, and a movement of parts is open, which the market might easily mishandle and overhaul. Despite the fact that some major participants in a few application programme zones are still unaware of the voltage, many of them initiate a watchful scenario or even enliven the stroll by introducing new terminal figures for the IoT and adding new components to it. As the Internet of Things develops, its potential for advancement is examined using a combination of associated development techniques and ideas, such as Cloud calculating, After Internet, Big Data, Robotics, and Semantic loan.

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

The Simulation is carried out using Proteus 8 software. It's a software package that includes schematic, simulation, and PCB design. ISIS is a programme that allows you to create schematics and simulate circuits in real time. The simulation allows for human interaction during the simulation, making it a real-time simulation. PCB design is done with ARES. It

offers the ability to display the output in a 3D representation of the designed PCB, including components. ISIS' library has a diverse set of components. It includes sources, signal generators, measuring and analysis instruments such as oscilloscopes, voltmeters, and ammeters, probes for real-time monitoring of circuit parameters, switches, displays, loads such as motors and lamps, discrete components such as resistors, capacitors, inductors, and transformers, and digital and analogue components such as resistors, capacitors, inductors, and transformers. Semiconductor integrated circuits. With surface mount and through hole packages, ARES can design PCBs with up to 14 inner layers. It has the footprints of various components such as ICs, transistors, headers, connections, and other discrete components integrated in it. The PCB Designer can choose between automatic and manual routing. The ARES schematic can be immediately transferred from the ISIS diagram.

Fig. 4. Simulation Result

VII. CONCLUSION

We can conclude from the above simulation that smart home automation can be constructed using a variety of technologies. The technologies outlined previously have both benefits and drawbacks. The major goal here is to increase the self-sufficiency of the elderly and physically challenged. A smart home system relieves stress by guaranteeing that your home is secure. In the future, artificial intelligence could be added to this field to further improve it.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

As a result, the simulation using Arduino, ESP8266, and IoT concept household appliances may be operated as follows. Any internet-connected device can access the appliances; however, in order to open a portal for controlling the appliances, we must input the local IP address in the URL of any browser.

XI. REFERENCES

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